

Welcome to the DATAMITE Newsletter

Our motto: Unleashing the Monetisation Potential of Data.

DATAMITE hosts its final event at the Data Spaces Symposium

The [Data Spaces Symposium](#) took place in Madrid, Spain, on 10–11 February. Hosted by the [Data Spaces Support Centre](#) (DSSC) in collaboration with [BDVA](#), [Gaia-X](#) and the [International Data Spaces Association](#), the symposium is the **premier global event dedicated to the future of data spaces**. It brings together pioneering thinkers, innovators and organisations that are shaping a connected, data-driven future. Under the motto ‘Accelerating adoption. Increasing Impact’, the 2026 edition showcased the ways in which data spaces facilitate collaboration and competitiveness, and demonstrate their global impact.

This marked **DATAMITE's** [third consecutive](#) year of [participation](#) at the Data Spaces Symposium. This edition was particularly important as it **hosted DATAMITE's final event**, bringing to a close over three years of intensive research, development and collaboration aimed at boosting data monetisation, interoperability, trading and exchange.

[Read the full article.](#)

 Highlights from the final event of DATAMITE

DATAMITE hosted its final event at the Data Spaces Symposium 2026, bringing over three years of intensive research, development and collaboration aimed at boosting data monetisation, interoperability, trading and exchange to a close.

This video showcases DATAMITE's time at the Symposium, including the final event. Do not miss it!

 Watch the DATAMITE final event

If you couldn't make it to the final event or would simply like to watch it again, you're in luck! You can **watch the full recording** on the [DATAMITE YouTube channel](#) or by pressing play above. Enjoy!

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